

FutuRSI paving the way

Six reasons why a German research software institution could and should be established

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This paper compiles six blog posts that were published by the FutuRSI project on its website in October and November 2025. The first drafts of these posts were produced following 18 expert interviews. This paper presents opinions on why a German research software institution should be established. The reasons are as follows: 1) research software is a central component of research practice; 2) research software engineering enables career advancement and connects technical and domain expertise; 3) increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of research software development is both necessary and possible; 4) proven national and international reference models point the way forward; 5) a national research software institution can be seamlessly integrated into the German research ecosystem; and 6) Germany needs to preserve its status as an attractive research location with excellent research software. Building on these six arguments, the FutuRSI project will develop a concrete concept and implementation plan and engage with stakeholders, facilitating their participation.

1 Introduction

This paper is a compilation of six blog posts published by the FutuRSi project on the FutuRSi website during October and November 2025. The first drafts of these posts were obtained as a result of 18 expert interviews, which also resulted in the key issues paper [1]. We conducted the expert interviews between July and September 2025 using a structured questionnaire via virtual communication tools. In this paper, we only present the summary of responses to the following questions:

- What specific advantages of an institution would most likely convince decision makers?
- What arguments can be used to win over sceptics?

The FutuRSi project will build on these six arguments, develop a concrete concept and implementation plan, engage with stakeholders and facilitate their participation. This paper presents opinion statements on why a German research software institution could and should be established. The reasons are:

1. Research software is a central component of research practice
2. Research software engineering enables career advancement and connects technical and domain expertise
3. Increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of research software development is both necessary and possible
4. Proven national and international reference models point the way forward
5. A national research software institution can be seamlessly integrated into the German research ecosystem
6. Germany needs to preserve its status as an attractive research location with excellent research software

2 Research software is a central component of research practice

Research software is now an indispensable part of scientific work, and its importance will only increase [2]. Modern research is simply no longer feasible without high-quality software of all types and categories [3]. Various studies have shown that better software leads to better research: research processes become more effective [4], impactful [5] and reproducible [6] – and in many cases are made possible in the first place. These effects are evident across the entire spectrum of scientific disciplines, e.g. from biology [7] to physics [8] and the social sciences [9], to energy research [10].

The significance of research software can be gauged by a number of indicators, including the importance of well-trained personnel in the field of research software development [11] and the number of topic-specific research software funding [12], as well as the specific funding requirements [13]. The growing awareness of the importance of research software is

also reflected in the extensive software holdings of the Software Heritage Archive, which reached over 20 billion unique source files in 2025 [14]. Moreover, the economic impact of open source software has been measured quantitatively, for example on the European economy [15], thereby demonstrating its impact far beyond the scientific domain. Nevertheless, quantifying the value of specific software in research contexts remains a particular challenge.

The development of specialised research software is an essential component of contemporary research methodologies and the relevance of research software is especially apparent in concrete instances of success: often, the value and reliability of scientific work can only be assured through adherence to specific quality criteria of the underlying software [16]. Advancements in the field, exemplified by a seminal paper authored by more than 5,000 researchers [17], have yielded a novel estimate of the Higgs boson's size: The ATLAS and CMS experiments at the Large Hadron Collider at CERN employed sophisticated data modelling and management software, underscoring the technological sophistication required for such endeavours. Another example is one of the most cited papers of all time: the short history of SHELX, a software suite for the determination of crystal structures [18]. Furthermore, the generation of visualisations and the interpretation of archaeological features of Maya ruins was only possible by the use of several research software [19]. Thus, in almost all disciplines, the following applies: without software, there is no data, and vice versa.

The establishment of a national research software institution could raise awareness among scientific institutions and advocate to science policymakers, ensuring that research software receives the recognition, support and continuous development that reflects its fundamental role in scientific practice, thereby establishing it as a first-class research output in its own right.

3 Research software engineering enables career advancement and connects technical and domain expertise

Software, as a product of human activity, requires continuous maintenance and further development. Enhanced recognition, reputation, and career paths for the people developing research software (research software engineers) are essential to attract and retain qualified professionals in this field. Advocacy for improved recognition and clearly defined career structures is therefore just as crucial as providing appreciation and professional development opportunities for those dedicated to developing and maintaining research software. However, there is often a significant discrepancy between the demand for research software development and the available training opportunities. Although training resources

are available, they sometimes fail to address the specific needs of their intended audience. Nevertheless, individuals who are experts in both software engineering and domain-specific research methodologies are already effectively providing research software as part of their work. But there is significant untapped potential in training, knowledge exchange and career advancement around research software. To improve career progression, institutions must recognise research software engineering as a core component of research work. They should also establish career paths tailored to specialised and general research software engineers. Furthermore, scientific communities must support their research software by publishing, citing and peer-reviewing it.

When research software engineering is successfully implemented, researchers can dedicate more time to their core activities. Acquiring programming skills and domain knowledge, identifying appropriate training venues, and taking on instructional roles requires more than individual effort. Research institutions must also foster a sense of comfort and belonging for research software engineers within academia. Additionally, the reputation of research software engineers must be strengthened. This cultural change bring about new forms of collaboration and belonging within the scientific system [20]. However, this change must be accompanied by legitimised and mandated actors.

A national research software institution can advocate for the recognition, reputation and career paths of research software engineers, while also helping them to establish their identity and sense of belonging within the scientific ecosystem by supporting the digital transformation in science in regard to research software.

4 Increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of research software development is both necessary and possible

The current heterogeneous and fragmented state of the German research software ecosystem results in considerable hidden costs and wasted resources. Numerous parallel structures exist, sometimes even within the same institution, which lead to redundant developments and inefficient, non-standardised custom-built solutions. Additionally, keeping up to date with diverse, parallel projects and initiatives, let alone understanding them, requires time and resources [21]. The present situation has now become so complex and diverse that the strict competitive logic of the German science system can no longer be the only driver and needs to be complemented by a logic of impact [22].

There is a more effective and efficient way forward: Local units or departments could benefit from operating under a larger umbrella [23] without sacrificing their autonomy [24]. Although community-driven, decentralised approaches to research software engineering are

important, establishing individual groups within each faculty or institute would be costly and disadvantage smaller, less well-resourced institutions. Also, centralising certain functions, such as higher degrees of networking and coordination [25, 26], could help create a more cost-efficient and effective research software development. Even though it does not always pay off in the short term, the development of joint research software could foster stronger collaboration by establishing interdisciplinary structures [27]. Thus, improving intra- and inter-organisational collaboration is particularly promising [28].

Local transfer approaches often result in limited user groups. A central unit or department could facilitate collaboration and coordination between different domain research groups, as well as between these groups and technical research or support staff [20]. More central consolidation could ensure everyone has access to all available knowledge and support the development and establishment of shared quality standards. Clear and transparent project governance, even if minimal, can help build trust in the project and its ability to evolve over time [29]. Although this restructuring poses challenges, particularly with regard to the redistribution of resources, greater structure and governance could help achieve the necessary effectiveness and efficiency improvements. However, the tension between these gains and institutional independence must be considered.

Another way to increase efficiency would be to better leverage the use of existing high-quality software. However, funders must recognise the value of supporting existing software through maintenance and use, and acknowledge the benefits of making strategic design decisions that require a higher initial investment but offer highly advantageous long-term effects on a software project's evolution [30]. This would enable research funds to be allocated more strategically to the continued development of existing relevant software, as well as new software with a good chance of long-term success. In this regard, encouraging the publication of research software with an open source software licence can make a software product less likely to become abandoned [31]. Currently, an open sharing practice is by no means the standard case [32].

A national research software institution can serve as a consolidation hub, making knowledge available centrally, and helping to avoid duplication of efforts. By providing coordinated structures and governance, it can establish best practices and contribute to significant efficiency gains throughout the scientific community while preserving local autonomy. To funding agencies and policymakers, it can serve as the unified voice of the community advocating for necessary change.

5 Proven national and international reference models point the way forward

There are numerous success stories, both domestically and abroad, that demonstrate the effectiveness of providing structured support for research in the digital age. This is why we have identified institutions that can help to leverage our initiative. Learning from the successes of initiatives and institutions can build momentum and demonstrate viable pathways forward. For instance, structures already exist around research data, texts and hardware that provide valuable support for researchers across the research ecosystem. These structures offer concrete opportunities for collaboration, coordination and knowledge exchange.

Germany already has successful horizontal structures in place from which lessons can be learned. The research data management ecosystem, comprising the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) and the data competence centres, can serve as a blueprint and a success story. Examples supporting high performance computing (HPC) include the regional bwHPC initiative¹ of the state of Baden-Württemberg and the cross-regional NHR Alliance², which demonstrate successful centralised coordination in related areas that could help provide core facilities with a new mission [33]. Furthermore, the recently institutionalized open-access.network³ provides transdisciplinary and centralised information on open access. Initiatives from other sectors focusing on software are particularly relevant. The Sovereign Tech Fund⁴ by the Sovereign Tech Agency is a prime example of successful open-source software funding. The Open Source Program Office initiative at the DigitalHub.SH⁵ in the state of Schleswig-Holstein demonstrates how open-source strategies can be supported at an institutional level.

At an international level, specific initiatives and institutions exist to centrally support the research software ecosystem nationally. A prime example is the UK's Software Sustainability Institute⁶, which has been helping people to build better and more sustainable research software since 2010. The Netherlands eScience Center⁷ also provides a strong national anchor point by concentrating the expertise in research software in a national centre. Another example is the Virtual Institute for Scientific Software⁸ by Schmidt Science, which offers an effective network transcending national borders. Furthermore, the training network "The Carpentries"⁹, which is integrated into other organisations and teaches foundational coding to researchers worldwide, demonstrates supranational success. These diverse reference models prove the effectiveness and feasibility of structured approaches, providing valuable

¹ <https://www.bwhpc.de/>

² National High Performance Computing: <https://www.nhr-verein.de/>

³ <https://open-access.network/>

⁴ <https://www.sovereign.tech/programs/fund>

⁵ <https://digitalhub.sh/>

⁶ <https://www.software.ac.uk/>

⁷ <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/>

⁸ <https://www.schmidtsociences.org/viss/>

⁹ <https://carpentries.org/>

blueprints for a German research software institution.

A national research software institution can learn from proven national and international success models and build on them. It can adopt best practices and benefit from the experience of established initiatives through targeted collaboration and exchange, while taking into account German-specific factors and conditions.

6 A national research software institution can be seamlessly integrated into the German research ecosystem

In order to be effective, a national research software institution must be integrated across the research ecosystem, both horizontally among different organisations and disciplines, and vertically from local structures to international partnerships. This level of integration is both necessary and achievable.

Showing where activities are already occurring in Germany is key to strategic positioning for such an institution. Currently, the system is not adequately equipped to incorporate software methods into research effectively and in the desired broad manner. While some actors in Germany are already in a relatively good position, having tailored research software policies, structures, and points of contact – the Helmholtz Association being a particularly positive example – others require stronger links to existing initiatives and structures. These existing strengths can serve as starting points for forming networks and demonstrate that foundational elements for a national research software institution are already in place.

A community-driven approach is crucial for the successful implementation of this integration. Scientific institutions and societies across all disciplines should play an active role in establishing and supporting a research software institution. Interdisciplinarity offers particularly promising opportunities: solutions developed in one field can be applied in others, accelerating innovation and reducing redundant problem-solving efforts.

It must also be acknowledged that funding for a research software institution requires strategic prioritisation within limited research budgets. A national institution should therefore actively demonstrate its commitment to overcoming existing challenges and needs. Identifying hotspots and existing initiatives helps to communicate a focus on strategic consolidation and targeted support rather than dispersed, ad hoc investments. It is therefore crucial to recognise the importance of continuous advocacy and participatory design processes in fostering acceptance within the scientific community.

By engaging with the community, conducting continuous advocacy activities and strategically connecting to existing structures, a national research software institution can achieve broad acceptance and effective integration. It can then serve as both an extension of and a consolidation point for Germany's research ecosystem.

7 Germany needs to preserve its status as an attractive research location with excellent research software

As a research and innovation hub, Germany must maintain its competitive edge by investing in high-quality research software and attracting the best talent in the field. This requires a broader consideration of the role of software in society. This includes maintaining public confidence in research by advocating for open and reproducible software. At the same time, the sovereignty of autonomous, resilient research institutions must be guaranteed in an increasingly digital research ecosystem with excellent research software.

Research software excellence can be characterised by technical aspects, like functionality and usability, as well as more general aspects such as the software's FAIRness, its openness and sustainability. Security and safety considerations also extend beyond technical aspects and include the reliability and sustainability of the software that underpins critical research. Against this background, the importance of reproducible research, digital sovereignty and the security of essential research software must be emphasised. All of these are crucial for maintaining the functionality of research in the digital age. This can only be achieved through social and organisational efforts, which are often cooperative in nature. However, German participation in the development of essential research software, such as the widely used PyTorch framework¹⁰, cannot be taken for granted. This circumstance raises the question of how much is actually "made in Germany", posing risks of exclusion and dependency. Also, Germany's appeal as a research destination hinges on the availability of viable career paths. Without structured support for research software practitioners, Germany risks losing talented researchers and software experts to countries with more established research software ecosystems. For example, there is an increasing acceptance of so-called "Research Technical Professional" roles in the British academic system. Additionally, the digital transformation of research, coupled with the increase in interdisciplinary and large-scale collaborative projects, has given rise to new professional identities that are blurring traditional boundaries, such as the binary classification of academic staff as either "scientific" or "technical/administrative". The ongoing integration of knowledge creation and research dependent on excellent software demonstrates the complex, hybrid nature of modern research

¹⁰ <https://pytorch.org/>

practices. It is high time that German universities and research institutions recognise and value the diverse contributions to research software excellence.

Furthermore, the increasing use of artificial intelligence (AI) methods, particularly generative models, as tools in all areas of research does not negate the need for human expertise. In our view, the argument that “AI will take over all software development in research” is invalid. While generative models can assist with coding when the fundamentals of software engineering are understood, it should be noted that using AI tools for software development may also present challenges regarding licensing new software or using code provided by a model [34]. To promote excellence in research software, it is essential to have individuals with a deep understanding of the underlying problem and a specific interest in knowledge. Therefore, human expertise, particularly in the form of personnel skilled in research software engineering, is essential to ensure the quality, suitability and integration of AI-generated solutions. Germany should provide these individuals with the necessary framework conditions and academic positions.

A national research software institution could strengthen the sovereignty and autonomy of research institutions in Germany and boost Germany’s appeal as a research location by promoting better career prospects for practitioners of research software with expertise in software development and AI usage, while also promoting excellence in research software engineering.

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